

Data are provided in the original Bruker format and in the standard format JCAMP.

Data to produce **Figures 2 a, b, c, d and e** are located in the corresponding folders *Figure 2a*, *Figure 2b*, *Figure 2c*, *Figure 2d* and *Figure 2e*. The JCAMP data are located in a unique folder *Figure 2* and the different file named regarding to the precise spectra.

Data to produce **Figures 3 a, b, c and d** are located in the corresponding folders *Figure 3a*, *Figure 3b*, *Figure 3c*, and *Figure 3d*.

Data to produce **Figures 4 b and d** are located in the folder *Figure4b_4d*. The experiments are organized as described in the following table:

Recycle delays	μ waves ON	μ waves OFF
1s	201	211, 215, 220
2s	202, 205	212, 216, 221
3s	203, 206	213, 217, 222
5s	204, 207	214, 218, 223

When several experiments number are indicated for similar experimental conditions, the spectra have been added before integration and enhancement measure.

Data to produce **Figure 4c** is located in the folder *Figure 4c*.